

The Impact of Climate Changes on Fisher Folk and Fisher Women Sustainable Poverty Livelihoods in Coastal Community of Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

This research examined the impact of climate change on fisher folk and fisher women sustainable poverty livelihoods in coastal community of thoothukudi. The principle of sustainable livelihood approach (SLA) is applied here and both qualitative and quantitative method including structural questionnaires, participatory rural appraisal (PRA), key informant interviews, and secondary sources were carried out to serve the objectives of the research. The changing scenario of climate events in terms of climate exposures and sensitivity has been perceived. Impact of this change and variability not just affects occupational activities but also hamper multifarious aspects of rural livelihoods that determine the extent of fisher's capacity to cope with climatic changes. A community-based development management approach undertaken in the watershed development programs including capacity building of communities is considered effective for enhancing climate-resilient fishing communities as well as for adapting to changes in climate variability with the technical and financial support from government and non-government organization.

Keywords: Climate Change; culture, Variability; Fisher Livelihoods; Coastal Community, Livelihood development, unpredictable climate change, Poverty, Natural disaster management.

Introduction

Coastal areas contribute significantly to the global economy by virtue of its natural resources, productive habitats and rich biodiversity. India with a long coastline of 8149 km supports almost 30 percent of its human population. Coastal fisheries are of immense importance as they provide livelihood opportunities for a large share of the population. The coastal state of Kerala is situated on the southwest coast of the Indian sub-continent, with an area of about 38,863 square kilometers and has a coastline of 589.5 kms, which apparently forms 10 percent of India's total coastline. The fisheries are a source of livelihood for the fishermen in Kerala, with

fishing being an imperative part of the economy of the state (Kurien, 2001). The climate change, the fisherfolk are naïve in context to the source of the problem, which includes temperature rise, extreme weather events, reduction in fish catch over years, change in fish composition over the years and sea level rise. The process of providing right and comprehensive knowledge on climate change is the need of the hour and this can be achieved through a bottom up approach involving the primary stakeholders along with the community which will eventually position them to adequate climate change adaptation and mitigation by augmenting their traditional knowledge (Shyam et al, 2013)

Objectives

1. To examine fishers women perception to climate change.
2. To analysis of the sustainable development livelihood of fisher folk.
3. To the impact of fisher women planning for the Coastal Community.

Primary data

Quantitative primary data were obtained through structured interview to determine the knowledge of men and women towards climate change. A questionnaire formulated with open and closed ended questions was administered the selected individual fishers. Quantitative Primary data were collected through key informant interview and FGD

Secondary data

Secondary data sources included the existing information, published and unpublished documents from BMU, fisheries officer. It includes different reports from the government and research which had information on climate change, gender among small scale fishers and food security village government office, ward government office, journals, books and dissertation from various institutions, such as) and non-governmental organizations dealing with issues pertaining to climate change, gender and food security.

Analysis of qualitative and quantitative data

Quantitative data were processed and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) computer software version 16.0 in order to get the frequency and percentages. Descriptive analysis was also used for analyzing verbal discussion.

Review

Adaptation refers to as adjustments in management strategies due to actual or expected changes in climatic conditions or their effects, in order to reduce risks or realize opportunities (Smit and Pilifisova, 2003). Adaptation takes different forms; it can occur at different scales and is undertaken by different people (for example, in the case of fisheries, these would be fishing net mending, fishing vessel repair, fish trading, fish processing or any other related activity at artisan level) (Bryant et al., 2000)

Climate change refers to a change in the state of the climate that can be identified by changes in variability of its properties and that persists for extended periods, typically decades or longer (IPCC, 2007). It is a long-term shift in the climate of a specific location, region or planet that is measured by changes in features associated with average weather, such variables are temperature, wind patterns, floods, droughts and precipitation. The causes of climate change are either natural or human-induced causes. UNFCCC (1992) defines climate change as “a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which in addition to natural climate that is observed over comparable time periods and thus affects food security

Problem Statement: Easter ling et al. (2008) infer with high confidence that subsistence farmers, pastoralists, and artisanal fisher folk will suffer complex, localized impacts from climate change. Climate change affects the poor through changes or depletion of common property/natural resources, such as fisheries, rangelands, or forests on which they depend on for their livelihoods. the impacts of climate change will be felt differently among regions, nations, communities, gender and age groups. Literature also reveals that little has been done in climate change and gender neutral, and therefore gender is an important determinant in climate change adaptations. women and youth are affected differently and often more severely by climate change and associated natural disasters such as floods, droughts, cyclones).

1.	Occupational uncertainty	70%
2.	Income disorganization	80%
3.	Equipments Damages and lost	85%
4.	Psycho-social problems	75%
5.	Poverty	90%

Effects of Climate Change on Fish

Fish are often largely affected by climate change as increasing temperature tends to affect every stage of their life cycle from their physiological, morphological, reproductive, migratory and behavioral responses (Daw et al., 2009). 2012). This is because time and locations of spawning of several species of fish are linked to physical conditions such as temperature, currents, as well as biological factors like food. Changes in these conditions on account of climate change would therefore impact negatively on the spawning of fishes in these habitats. Likewise, food and feeding of fish would be affected as plankton production in aquatic ecosystem is linked to physicochemical variables of the ecosystem which could be seriously affected by change in the climate (Ayub, 2010).

Impact of Climate Change on Resources Perception Analysis

In the context of the study, resources indicate the fisheries sector, its allied activities and the inventories involved. In order to rank the perception of fisher households towards the different parameters affecting climate change on resources, respondents were asked to prioritise their perceptions on different factors namely shift in spawning seasons (SSS), migration of fishes (MoF), varied catch composition (VCC), catch reduction (CR), increased effort in fishing(IEF), alterations in fishing seasons(AFS), non-availability of regular species(NRS), occurrence of invasive species (OIS)), temporal shift in the species availability (TSA), loss in craft and gear (LCG) and depletion of farm inventories (DFI).

Fisher Folk

If the aim of the project is to assist fisher folk who want to get organised and sustain their organisations, then one of the critical first steps is to understand fisher folk and their perspectives on fisheries matters. We need to appreciate what the incentives for organising are, and how best to manage conflict within our Caribbean culture. Unless fisher folk genuinely want to organise, perhaps after participating in awareness and capacity building programmes, it is unlikely that their organisations will be established or be sustainable. Global experience shows that FFOs formed without high demand from the fisher folk themselves fail even if they get assistance

Sustainable Livelihoods of Fisher Folk

The Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA) perceived as a way of looking at how an individual, a household or a community secures its well-being over time (Serrat, 2008; Carney, 2002). Livelihood in the context of the SLA is made up of the abilities, the assets (stores, resources, claims and access) and activities required for day-to-day living. It doesn't only take account of monetary income but also the other forms of capital that people have access to, including social assets, physical assets, natural assets and human capital that can help in adapting climate change for enhancing food security. A study conducted by Wall and Marzall (2004), has designed assets types to assess adaptive capacity for meeting challenges posed by climate change. In their research they interpreted that adaptive capacity depends in part on the available social, human, natural and economic resources

Sustainable Organizations

- A strategic and participatory planning process
- A competent elected leadership with advisers
- Regular meetings with members and partners
- A means of communicating regularly with members
- A means of delegating tasks and responsibilities
- Orientation and training for new (board) members
- Social time together to strengthen social networks
- Working relationships with powerful key players
- A diversified and flexible sound financial portfolio

Sustainable Financing

- Financial (funds needed; revenue generation, flow)
- Legal (legal support for financing; new laws needed)
- Administrative (collection; enforcement; corruption)
- Social (willingness to pay; equity; poverty impacts)
- Political (government support; enabling policy; risk)
- Environmental (impacts; uncertainty; irreversibility)

Mobilizing fisher folk: Crises are good incentives around which to mobilise. They prompt collective action, learning and adaptation in a short time. Is there a crisis in the fishery or location that you are concerned with? Threats must be real and immediate, but can often come from either the harvest or post harvest parts of the fish chain. Since all parts of the chain are linked, what affects one part of the fishing industry often impacts on others. Determine incentives for organizing (discussed earlier) and see if there are any threats that highlight the urgency to get organized.

No	Fishers' perception on climate change Statement	%
1.	Traditional perception of climate change as a curse from God lead to food insecurity	60
2.	Climate change lead to disappearance of fish species	70
3.	Rainfall fluctuation occurring in recent years is the affect of climate change	40
4.	Climate change have a big impact in fish production	65
5.	Artisanal fishers are locality pertaining climate change information	75
6.	Artisanal fishers play a great role in climate change perception	80
7.	Artisanal fisher folk low adaptive capacity to climate change	85
8.	Climate change affects artisanal fishers differently depending on their abilit	65
9.	No relationship between climate change and rain pattern	50

- About half (62%) of the fishers practiced agriculture activity but they grew only bitter cassava and sweet potatoes as they were the only food crop that could grow under the sand soil. Few (7.9%) of the fishers practiced vegetable faming along the lake banks, there were also 18.9% of fishers who were carpenters and tailors, most of these tailors and carpenters were disabled persons. Few fishers (3.7%) in the study area practiced livestock keeping. However, there were 20% of fishers who did not practice any activity apart from fishing, during non- fishing season they stayed
- Majority (90%) of fishers used to change fishing grounds depending on the availability of catch in the area; this means that they didnt catch fish in the same area daily, whereas 1.1% of fishers caught fish in the same ground and 9.6% of the fishers used .180 000 to hire the fishing gear and majority (79%) of fishers were given gears by the fish agents, on the condition that they had to sell the captured fish to the same agent . Other minor activities were carried out on temporal basis (vegetable selling, carpentry and tailoring) during non fishing season. Nevertheless, all artisanal fisher folk depended on fishing for their livelihood.
- Fishers against Climate Change Impact Adaptive strategies are important measures that enable people to absorb the impact of shock (for any emergence). Communities have different levels of coping strategies that allow them either respond to hazards or to prevent potential hazard. Communities with greater adaptive capacity face a lower risk of disaster.

Findings of the Study

- The fishermen were of the opinion that major changes in climatic parameters had occurred in the last 10 years, particularly after the tsunami in 2004. Fishermen ranked wind direction/speed as the most important climatic parameter that had changed significantly over the years followed by temperature and current.
- They pointed out that though climate change was one of the reasons for declining fish catch, the major reason was overfishing by mechanized trawlers using Chinese engines and exploitation of juveniles.
- The fisherfolk said that they found it very difficult to predict climatic events like in earlier years due to large unexpected seasonal variations. For example, they were unable to understand the

current flow direction as it was very irregular and unpredictable due to rough ocean conditions, which led to difficulty in predicting fish availability.

- Fishermen suggested that the government should bring regulations on craft, gear, period, fish species and related aspects, to maintain sustainable fishing.

Suggestions

1. Conducting awareness programmed to redeem them from their poverty these will include encourage them to save at least a minimum amount from their earnings. Encourage them to live a contended life with what they have.
2. In order to spend the time fruitfully they should be encouraged to occupy themselves with some form of self employment particularly off season in fishing.
3. The government should pay their attention to recover socio economic condition of families affected by the unpredictable climate change. Particularly, the government should provide necessary support to fishing labourers-families. Because, they are suffering to manage their day to day life for the reason of impact of unpredictable climate change.
4. The government should provide the compensation to person who lost their fishing equipments due to the unpredictable climate change.
5. The village dweller told that, the government doesnot provide the loan for upgrading their work condition. So the government should even arrange or provide a loan for the labourer fishermen or small boat owner to start the fishing activities individually.

Conclusion

Diversification of activities is one of the presumptions of enhancing food security to artisanal fisher folk and to adapt with climate change. The research results shows that the sustainability of fishers-livelihoods of Lake Victoria at Rorya District are insecure due to poor management of resources, limited ability to adapt climate change as the fishers depend almost solely on fishing activity as their source of generating income. Fishers- perception on climate change among artisanal fishers is still very low. It is due to lack of education and attainment, unequal resource access and control among gender such as women and disabled have access to resource but lack control over the resource. Majority of the artisanal fisher folk have attained primary school level of education that it become too difficult to adapt or have the ability to climate change and enhance food security. Inefficient of fishers cooperatives/associations seemed to be an obstacle for fishers to rescue their livelihood when there is a change in climate that fish disappear due to climate change, they could have solidarity to overcome that climate change or adapt to it and continue to have food. Savings and credits for fishers would be solved through cooperative since they will be able to stand as one and speak with one voice thus have ability to climate change. The absence of basic social services near fishing grounds like health centres, clean and safe water supplying systems, poor communication systems.

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